

Heterogeneous Ion-Selective Electrodes Based on Electro-neutral Ion-Carriers : Barium(II) and Nickel(II) Electrodes

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Heterogeneous barium(II) and nickel(II) selective electrodes based on electroneutral complexes, formed from cyclic ligands 2,3-benzo-1,4,7,10,13-pentaoxacyclopentadeca-2-ene for Ba(II); and 1,4,8,11-tetraazocyclotetradecane for Ni(II) have been described. The electrodes have short response time, are mechanically stable and give fairly constant potentials within a wide range of pH. The selectivity coefficients, determined by mixed solution method, for a number of cations are found to be less than unity for both the electrodes. The electrodes have been found to be satisfactory in electrometric titrations. Using the Ni(II)-electrode, the stability constant of 1 : 1 nickel-sulphosalicylic acid complex was determined, $\log K_1 = -9.07$ (30° , $I \approx 0.005$).

ION-selective electrodes based on liquid membranes are well known¹⁻³. These membranes contain either dissolved ion-exchangers or electroneutral ion-carriers. In the latter case, the membrane consists of a suitable inert organic solvent with a dissolved macrocyclic substance which may be an antibiotic, a macrotetrolide, a cyclic polyether or a macromolecular acyclic compound⁴. The structure of the macrocyclic substance favours the formation of a polar cavity in which a specific ion can be enclosed because of ion-dipole interactions. However, the construction of such an electrode poses mechanical problems⁵. The liquid phase containing the electroactive material must be immiscible with the test solution, the loss of the liquid by evaporation should be minimum, and the concentration of the electroactive substance in the membrane should remain uniformly constant. To overcome these difficulties, it was thought worthwhile to prepare a heterogeneous membrane with the electroneutral complex held in a fixed matrix, thus overcoming the problems encountered with a liquid membrane. An attempt has therefore been made to construct electrodes for Ba(II) and Ni(II), using the metal complex as well as the ligand alone, as electroactive materials. For Ba(II) ion, the polyether, 2,3-benzo-1,4,7,10,13-pentaoxacyclopentadeca-2-ene (benzo-15-crown-5) and for Ni(II) ion, 1,4,8,11-tetraazocyclotetradecane (cyclam-14) have been employed as ligand. The electrodes are similar to the solid state ones.

Experimental

Preparation of Ba(II) complex : The complex of Ba(II) with benzo-15-crown-5 was prepared by the method of Pederson⁶. To a solution of 400 mg of $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH AnalaR) in 5 ml methanol, 900 mg of the crown ether was added and dissolved by stirring at room temperature. The solution was allowed to evaporate at room temperature ($\sim 30^\circ$) for several days, till the complex was obtained in

the form of a slurry. This was dried by pressing between filter papers, washed with a small quantity of methanol and dried again at room temperature.

Preparation of membrane : In order to provide mechanical strength to liquid membranes, a layer of PVC to support the liquid has sometime been adopted^{7,8}. Problems like immiscibility of liquid and solution, loss by evaporation etc. still remain. Hence in the present studies epoxy resin (Araldite, Ciba India Ltd.) was employed to obtain the membranes, which gave well defined interface and enhanced the mechanical resistance to stirring and pressure effects. The membranes were solid state and were obtained as described elsewhere⁹.

The following membranes (master disc) were obtained by mixing the electroactive materials and Araldite :

- (i) 100 mg of benzo-15-crown-5 + 150 mg of Araldite.
- (ii) 100 mg of the barium complex + 150 mg of Araldite.
- (iii) 100 mg each of cyclam-14 and Araldite.
- (iv) 100 mg each of nickel complex and Araldite.

The electrodes using the above membranes were called, I, II, III and IV, respectively.

Preparation of electrode : To prepare the electrodes, a piece of membrane ~ 1 cm in diameter was cut out from the respective master disc and fixed at one end of a 10 cm long glass tube (inner diam ~ 8 mm) with Araldite. In the first two electrodes the internal solution kept was $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ BaCl}_2$, while in the other two it was $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. A saturated calomel electrode (SCE) served for electrical contact.

Instruments : A digital pH-meter (Systronics, Model 335) with a second SCE as reference was used for electrode potential measurements. Measurements were made at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

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Results and Discussion

Electrode response : The response of electrodes I and II in solutions of BaCl_2 of different concentrations was followed with the aid of the pH-meter. Initially, electrode I gave linear response in the concentration range $1 \times 10^{-1} - 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of BaCl_2 and the slope was *ca* 43 mV per decade change in concentration. However, the electrode was unsuitable for work, since with passage of time, it gave erratic response and the linearity was lost.

Electrode II gave linear response down to $5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ with a slope value 46 in the first week, but the value changed to 38 mV per decade change in concentration in the second week. (Fig. 1) which remained constant for atleast 5 weeks. The analytical range of the electrode could be extended down to $5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of Ba(II) . The electrode gave excellent response also in aqueous ethanol medium (Fig. 1).

The response of electrodes III and IV were

Fig. 1. Calibration curve for electrode II, A : 60% ethanol solution ; B : 40% ethanol solution ; C : aqueous solution.

Fig. 2. Calibration curve for electrode IV, A : 40% ethanol solution ; B : aqueous solution ; C : 20% DMF solution.

recorded at different concentrations of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. Electrode III failed to give uniformly a linear response and was not considered useful. During the first four days of its preparation, electrode IV showed linear response down a concentration of 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} of $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ with a slope of 44 mV per decade change in concentration. In the second week, however, a linear response down to 5×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} of $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ with 39 as slope value was observed (Fig. 2). Though the value of 39 is slightly higher than the expected Nernstian value in the case of a bivalent ion, the value did not change atleast for 8 weeks. Linear response was also observed in 40% aqueous-ethanol and in 20% aqueous-dimethylformamide (Fig. 2).

Both in case of electrodes II and IV, 80% of the total potential was reached within 20 seconds when concentration of BaCl_2 or $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was varied from 0.01 to 0.001 mol dm^{-3} . After 40 seconds, the potential got stabilised and remained constant thereafter.

Effect of pH: The potential remained constant in the pH range 3.5–8.0 for both electrodes II and IV (Fig. 3). This indicates the working ranges of pH for the electrodes.

Fig. 3. Potential—pH diagram for electrodes II (curve 1) and IV (curve 2).

Interference by ions: The cationic interferences due to other ions were studied by the determination of selectivity coefficients by mixed solution method^{8,7}. The electrode potentials were recorded in mixed solutions having a fixed concentration of interferant, B (1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) and varying concentrations (1×10^{-1} to 1×10^{-8} mol dm^{-3}) of either BaCl_2 or $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (M). The selectivity coefficients were calculated from the plot of potential of electrodes system vs concentration in the usual manner^{8,7,10} (Table 1). The values of selectivity coefficients are less than unity in all the cases. However, for electrode II, the value for $\text{Mg}(\text{II})$ and for electrode IV, the value for $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ approach unity. The value < 1 suggests⁷ that the electrode responds selectively to $\text{Ba}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ in presence of a number of other ions.

The calibration curves were drawn by taking measurements in two different salts of $\text{Ba}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ ion. It was found that in the cases of both $\text{Ba}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ electrodes, chloride and nitrate solutions

gave identical curves. Consequently either of the solutions can be used for calibration purposes.

TABLE 1—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS ($K_{M,B}$) OF ELECTRODES II AND IV IN MIXED SOLUTIONS AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$

Foreign ion	Selectivity coefficient	
	Electrode II	Electrode IV
K^+	0.80	(a)
Na^+	0.41	0.08
NH_4^+	0.56	(a)
Mg^{2+}	0.90	0.38
Ca^{2+}	0.62	0.31
Sr^{2+}	0.50	(a)
Mn^{2+}	(a)	0.65
Co^{2+}	(a)	0.95
Cu^{2+}	(a)	0.62
Zn^{2+}	0.75	0.42
Cr^{3+}	(a)	0.02
Al^{3+}	(a)	0.04

(a) Not determined.

Applications: The utility of electrodes II and IV in analytical studies was established by electro-metric titrations of Ba^{2+} against SO_4^{2-} using electrode II, and Ni^{2+} against EDTA using electrode IV, both of which gave satisfactory results.

Ion-selective electrodes have been used in the direct determination of the free metal ion concentration in metal-ligand equilibria¹⁰⁻¹². The stability constant of the complex in solution can be evaluated therefrom. The stability constant of 1 : 1 $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ -sulphosalicylic acid (SSA) complex has been determined to further illustrate the use of electrode IV.

SSA has three ionizable protons, the proton from the sulphonic acid group dissociates completely¹³ at $\text{pH} \sim 1$, and consequently, in aqueous solution, the ligand exists as H_2L^- . The metal-ligand equilibria are (charges are omitted):

Eq. 1 represents the formation of 1 : 1 species and the total metal ion concentration is given by

$$\text{M}^0 = [\text{M}^{2+}] + [\text{ML}^-] \dots 3$$

from which K_1 works out to be

$$K_1 = \frac{\left\{ \frac{\text{M}^0}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}] - 1} \right\}}{[\text{L}^{3-}]} \dots 4$$

where, $[\text{L}^{3-}]$ is the free ligand concentration and can be evaluated from the expression¹⁴

$$[\text{L}^{3-}] = \frac{\text{L}^0 - \{\text{M}^0 - [\text{Ni}^{2+}]\}}{\phi} \dots 5$$

In eq. 5, L^0 is the total ligand concentration and ϕ is given by

$$\phi = 1 + \frac{[\text{H}]}{K_3} + \frac{[\text{H}]^2}{K_2 K_3} \dots 6$$

K_2^{H} and K_3^{H} are the equilibrium constants corresponding to the dissociation of carboxyl and phenolic hydrogens respectively, and $[\text{H}]$ is the hydrogen ion concentration.

A series of solutions were prepared in which the concentrations of metal and ligand were kept constant, but pH was varied in the range 4.5–5.3, where only the 1:1 species are formed^{1b}. The electrode potential of each solution was measured and the corresponding values of $[Ni^{2+}]$ were obtained from the calibration curve. The dissociation constant (at $I \approx 0.005$) being known^{1a}, the free ligand concentration and therefrom the value of $\log K_1$ was calculated to be 9.07. The value agreed with that determined by Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{1a}.

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